

Workplace Discrimination through an Intersectional Lens: A Comprehensive Review of Individual and Social Factors

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Women constitute more than half of the world's population, and gender is a socially constructed concept rather than a biologically determined basis for discrimination. Workplace discrimination against women in India is a long-standing problem that has the potential to affect women's overall well-being. This review paper critically examines studies conducted on women, with particular attention to employed Muslim women. It discusses various forms of workplace discrimination, including the gender pay gap, occupational segregation, limited career opportunities, and biases in hiring and promotion. Articles were collected from several electronic databases, including PubMed, APA-PsycArticles, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Google Scholar, and JSTOR. A combination of keywords related to workplace discrimination was used to find relevant articles, including "Muslim women" OR "employed Muslim women" OR "women at intersections" OR "minority women" AND "workplace discrimination" OR "gender discrimination" OR "religious discrimination" AND "identity" OR "religious identity" OR "feminist identity" AND "coping self-efficacy" OR "social support" OR "resilience" OR "courage to challenge" AND "job commitment" OR "life satisfaction" OR "psychological well-being." The study only considered English language publications and all accessible publications were reviewed using institutional subscription. Both national and international studies were carefully reviewed and combined. The review highlights the necessity of exploring the experiences of employed Muslim women, particularly in contexts marked by pronounced structural inequalities like in India, in order to inform broader efforts aimed at enhancing the ability of minority women to succeed within diverse and complex work-life settings.

Keywords: Muslim women, intersectionality, workplace discrimination, religious and gender identity

Women across societies have historically been demoralized psychologically, socially, physically, and economically, and this is often justified by religion or traditional social practices (Jalali, 2003). Women positioned at intersections may be treated unfairly at workplaces not only because they are women but also because of the characteristics that have nothing to do with their work performance, such as gender, religion, race, age, or sexual orientation (Chung, 2001). Even though women now have more access to education and professional training than they had in the past, equal access has not been reflected in equal outcomes in the labor market. Women remain underrepresented in many sectors and have higher chances of being employed in part-time jobs (ILO, 2023).

The gender pay gap is an explicit indication of inequality. Across many countries, women are paid less than men, even when they have the same level of education and work experience (OECD, 2023). Earlier explanations for this disparity were based on differences in educational qualifications (Goldin, 2014); however, this argument no longer carries much weight, and women have pretty much bridged

this education gap. Research indicates that this issue is more concerned with how the structural system works. Traditional jobs that are usually done by women are often paid less and not valued as much as jobs usually done by men (ILO, 2023). Similarly, women are less likely to be selected for leadership roles, particularly jobs in a male-dominated field (Kricheli-Katz, 2019). Sometimes, they are more liable to be judged more harshly than men, especially if they behave in an assertive way. Mothers are also known to earn less and have decreased opportunities to advance in their careers compared to women without children (Correll et al., 2007). In India, women have only restricted opportunities because of the workplace regulations and cultural expectations (Buddhapriya, 2009). In fields like Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), most of the employees are men, indicating an apparent gender gap (UNESCO Institute of Statistics & ILO, 2020). Researchers argue that such disparities are not due to biological differences but rather due to social norms in the workplace that discriminate against men and women unequally (Ridgeway, 2011). Even though there are advanced policies to protect women from discrimination, they still face many challenges at work.

This article reviews existing studies on workplace discrimination faced by employed Muslim women, with a focus on the personal and social factors that may affect their resilience and overall well-being. Relevant studies were collected using electronic databases, such as PubMed, APA PsycArticles, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Google Scholar, and JSTOR. Key words used in the search included workplace discrimination, Muslim women, religion, employed women, identity, and resilience. Some of the key terms that helped locate relevant studies were "Muslim women" OR "employed Muslim women" OR "women at intersections" OR "minority women" AND "workplace discrimination" OR "gender

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discrimination” OR “religious discrimination” OR “intersectionality” AND “religious identity” OR “feminist identity” AND “coping self-efficacy” OR “social support” OR “resilience” OR “courage to challenge” AND “job commitment” OR “life satisfaction” OR “psychological well-being.” Keywords were also interchanged to locate those studies that specifically examine the context of Muslim women in India.

Muslim Women and Workplace Inequality

Negative stereotypes about Muslims affect the way employers think and behave (YouGov, 2015). Research shows that Muslim candidates have a lower chance of getting an interview call than an equally qualified non-Muslim. This practice is referred to as “Muslim penalty” (Lancee, 2019). This disadvantage is more evident when Muslim women express their visibility in terms of dressing, like wearing hijab. They may also face biased questions related to marriage or parenting, experience presuppositions that they are less determined in their work (ENAR, 2016) and are less likely to get promotions. Official reports indicate that grievances regarding religious discrimination are on the rise, with Muslim women having frequent complaints of unfair treatment during hiring and in the workplace (EEOC, 2021). The same trends are also found in Asian countries. It is reported that in Malaysia, certain women are not allowed to follow their religion in their workplaces, including not being allowed to take prayer breaks or even wear the hijab (Mokhtar et al., 2022).

Importantly, it has to be understood that Muslims are not a uniform society, but employers tend to look at them as a homogenous group based on negative assumptions. For instance, it has been found that having an Arab-sounding name can decrease the odds of securing a job interview (Arai & Thoursie, 2009). This paper focuses on the issue of workplace discrimination through the lens of intersectionality, which allows examining how different elements of identity interact with each other and influence experiences. In India, the experiences of Muslim women are largely influenced by gender, religion, and certain social, cultural, and economical circumstances peculiar to the nation. Hence, their realities at the workplace should be understood with some reference to the local context, where such overlapping identities are located.

Women at Indian Workplaces

Women usually have to make challenging career decisions, and this pressure becomes stronger in a society where gender inequality is intense (Hassanzadeh et al., 2014). This disparity is associated with social conventions that place family and domestic burdens on women, restricting their career growth (Jayachandran, 2015). The economic participation of women in India remains low, which indicates that the structural constraints remain in place even after attempts to increase equality in the workplace (World Economic Forum, 2025).

As per the data published by the Periodic Labour Force Survey (2022-23), the monthly income of women with regular urban jobs is approximately 4,800/-, and men approximately 6,300/-, which is a wage difference of approximately 24%. This shows more profound injustices, such as women being concentrated in low-paying roles (Sengupta & Puri, 2021). Studies have found that such disparities are not primarily associated with reduced ability and education but because of the discrimination and structural constraints (Das &

Desai, 2003). Corporate statistics also revealed that women constitute a very small percentage of the workforce at about 26%. Women's representation at high levels, such as C-suite positions, is approximately 18-19%, and only 8% are in the position of CEO (Biswas, 2024). Many women complain of being biased and insensitively treated at work, and some report sexual harassment. However, the formal complaints submitted on these issues are less than half, and this indicates a lack of trust in the grievance systems (Aon, 2024). Recent statistics also indicate that the proportion of women in regular wage-paid employment in urban India has decreased, and many are shifting to informal or self-employment (Nisha, 2024).

Indian women also experience barriers that may be described as a “glass ceiling,” which hinders the upward mobility of women to higher levels (Basu & Sinha, 2021). Their progress is further limited by harassment, unequal promotions, job insecurity, and poor institutional protection, particularly in male-dominated and private-sector workplaces (Rajesh & Manoj, 2016). Along with all of this, family and the need to care are still predominantly tied to a woman, which influences their career development (Golpelwar, 2015); for example, the chances of jobs getting back to mothers are lower, particularly when it comes to patrilineal societies (Bedi et al., 2018). The collective disadvantages among women are more powerful when marginalized in terms of religious, caste, and class differences (Dewan, 2024)

Intersectional Bias in Indian Workplaces

The dual disadvantage may restrict women's access to decent working opportunities. Compared to other religious communities, Muslims report high rates of perceived unfair treatment, particularly in employment (Niazi, 2022). Muslim women are biased in jobs and are usually restricted to informal jobs and are underemployed regardless of qualifications (Sachar Committee Report, 2006). Their workplace inclusion is also influenced by cultural stereotypes and prejudice (Amin, 2022). Research reports reveal that early marriage, low literacy rates, and lack of decision-making power by Muslim women have been at high levels, and this limits their access to education and ability to become independent (Hasan & Menon, 2004). Some are also prone to othering at work, whether wearing or not wearing the hijab in the workplace, which impacts their confidence and belongingness (Khan et al., 2025). Even though Muslim women remain in the job through internal strength and support from social networks (Yousef-Morgan & Luthans, 2007) discrimination continues to have serious consequences on them. Studies reveal that discrimination in the workplace lower job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and overall well-being (Ensher et al., 2001).

Intersecting Identities of Employed Muslim Women

Religion is not merely some personal belief; it defines the way many women live, work, and see themselves. Faith provides a sense of belonging, strength, and meaning to many Muslim women (Mahmood, 2005). However, in the workplace, religious identity is visible through visible behaviors, such as wearing hijab or taking prayer breaks, which may sometimes cause colleagues to become uncomfortable (King & Franke, 2016). This may influence recruitment, promotions, and daily treatment in the workplace

(Ghumman & Jackson, 2008). Sometimes, employees who seek religious accommodation are retaliated against or even pressured to remain silent (Ghumman et al., 2013). At the same time, workplaces that accommodate religious practices also report higher job satisfaction and employee engagement (Messarra, 2014) which have also been found to relieve stress and ease human experiences in challenging situations (Dik et al., 2024).

Feminist identity is another important part of women's self-understanding. It evolves when women start realizing inequality and start challenging injustice (Downing & Roush, 1985). Feminist women can understand discrimination and confront unfair practices in the workplace (Czopp & Monteith, 2003). It is also associated with better coping abilities, resilience, and well-being (Moradi & Subich, 2002). Nevertheless, many women do not identify themselves as 'feminists' due to stigma or even socially enforced influences (Aronson, 2003). Religion and gender are the two elements influencing the identity of Muslim women. Traditional expectations may turn women into individuals whose primary identity is their family roles (Ghomi, 2019) which is further complicated in India by their minority status (Haq et al., 2020). Women who identify themselves as feminists are able to fight inequality and ensure well-being (Lee & Wessel, 2022). These two identities influence the work experience of Muslim women, their reactions to discrimination, and their ability to remain confident, dedicated, and self-fulfilled.

Psychological Resources: Coping Self-efficacy and Courage to Challenge

Internal strength affects the way women react to discrimination at work. In cases where women experience unfair treatment or are pushed aside, their capacity to respond to such situations becomes quite significant. Coping self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in the ability to cope with stress using effective coping responses (Chesney et al., 2006). Women who believe they can handle problems are more likely to stay calm, think clearly, and are able to find solutions (Benight & Bandura, 2004). It has been revealed that the protective effect of coping self-efficacy lowers distress and enhances psychological well-being (Benka et al., 2014). Turning to religious belief, support from family members, or community networks are considered as a way of coping (Ahmed et al., 2017). When women feel confident in their ability to cope, they are less likely to feel helpless in the face of discrimination.

Another key individual factor is courage to challenge. It is defined as readiness to voice an objection to unfair treatment, even when there is personal risk (Detert & Bruno, 2017). Where there is bias in the workplace, it might be safer to be silent, but it might also strengthen inequality. Courage enables women to challenge injustices in unfair decisions, demand equal opportunities, and defend their rights. It has been found that courage is associated with resilience, persistence, and life satisfaction (Magnano et al., 2021). A visible Muslim woman fighting a discrimination battle may demand more courage because of the added scrutiny from others (Gilliat-Ray, 2010). When women are empowered to act courageously, challenge the status quo, and express themselves, it leads to a better chance of maintaining a positive state of mind that fosters resilience and organizational achievement (Bai et al., 2023). Job resources like autonomy, feedback, and learning opportunities tend to reinforce both courage and thriving, as these lead to a sense of purpose and responsibility (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Employees who feel

that the work they are engaged with is meaningful and feel themselves responsible for the decisions will be more willing to push boundaries and be actively involved in the organizational roles when they feel that what they do matters (Hackman, 1980). Though there is limited research on courage as a psychological perspective, existing studies consistently highlight its importance as a personal resource. Courage has been positively associated with self-efficacy, persistence, and resilience (Hannah et al., 2007). It helps individuals to face a challenge, manage fear, and stay focused on the right things despite pressure (May et al., 2003). Courageous leaders are usually viewed as more efficient and more likely to motivate people to succeed individually and collectively (Sosik et al., 2012). Courage has been positively linked with life satisfaction (Santisi et al., 2020), psychological and subjective well-being (Gustems & Calderon, 2014), and career adaptability (Sovet et al., 2017). These findings affirm courage to challenge as a foundational construct for resilience, growth, and thriving, particularly for women navigating intersecting social and professional constraints. Courage has largely been explored as a moral virtue rather than as a psychological strength. This calls for a broader exploration of courage as a meaningful resource in the lived experiences of intersectional women.

Role of Social Support in Women's Lives

Social support means having people who care, listen, guide, and help when needed (Ioannou et al., 2019). Studies indicate that the more people feel supported, the more they report increased life satisfaction and emotional well-being (Barringer et al., 2016). It does not necessarily mean the assistance itself, but rather the sense one experiences in a difficult situation that the support is available if needed (Moradi & Funderburk, 2006). Women feel more relaxed and remain motivated in their jobs when their families are supportive and encouraging (Utaminingsih et al., 2016). In the workplace, supportive supervisors and colleagues may enhance job satisfaction and help alleviate stress (Aryee, 1992). Research studies further show that social support has predictive power for life satisfaction and psychological well-being (Akanni & Oduaran, 2018). However, gender roles and religious expectations determine the type of support available to Muslim women in India (Mahmood, 2005). The presence of cultural values that uphold modesty and household duty might restrict involvement in the outside world, which is essential to pursue further learning and career growth. For Muslim women, support from family, peers, or community strengthens their sense of belonging and helps them cope with exclusion (Mahmood, 2005). Resilience studies have also found social support as a key factor that enable people to adapt to adversity (Fleming & Ledogar, 2008). Greater support is attributed to improvement in mental health, happiness, and even increased longevity (Cobb, 1976). It helps in reducing the impact of stress and discrimination by providing emotional and practical support (Folkman & Lazarus, 1991). When people have strong social connections, it may help to improve self-esteem and give them a sense of belonging, which is essential for overall well-being (Ajrouch et al., 2010). Social support is regarded as an effective resource in the workplace that enables employees to cope with work demands and be committed to their jobs (Demerouti et al., 2001). Nevertheless, researchers suggest that workplace support might not positively affect women in the same way as it does for men, perhaps due to increased emotional stress and multiple

responsibilities among women (Bergeron et al., 2020). It has become evident from existing literature that social support plays an important role, especially in the lives of women at intersections. In India, where Muslim women are forced to choose between their gender roles, their religious affiliation, and their professional requirements, social support may serve as an important resource that enhances their resilience, defends their well-being, and makes them devoted to work.

Research Gaps and Future Directions

Earlier research has broadly reported challenges faced by women in different social and workplace settings. However, there is still a lack of research specifically on employed Muslim women in India. Looking at their experiences through an intersectional lens helps us understand how different identities interact to shape their personal and professional lives. At the same time, applying an intersectional perspective also presents analytical challenges, as it requires attention to both the structural barriers women face and the personal and social resources they draw upon to maintain resilience. In addition, most of the existing literature has been shaped by sociological, gender, or organizational paradigms and has given more attention to barriers. However, while these aspects are critical, studies overlooked how it works in a resilience paradigm. Based on the literature reviewed, the present paper introduces the gaps in the literature that require filling and the necessity of an integrated, intersectional, and resilience-based approach. This paper also provides a foundation for a more complete understanding of how individual, social, and workplace conditions work together to influence the resilience and well-being of employed Muslim women.

Conclusion

In India, women are often influenced by traditional gender roles, religious expectations, and cultural restrictions that limit their participation in social life and career choices. These realities, when combined with discrimination in the workplace and a lack of institutional support, make Muslim women vulnerable to psychological stress and social exclusion. The reviewed literature clearly demonstrates that women's workplace experiences are influenced by discrimination, gendered expectations, and limited institutional support. These insights gained from the existing literature are expected to inform both policy and practice, which may help organizations to design inclusive workplace policies, mentorship programs, and support systems that recognize and address the unique experiences of minority women. Moreover, these findings may be used to support social and governmental initiatives promoting women's empowerment, equity, and their roles in public life. Through this comprehensive literature review, the study highlights the necessity of exploring the experiences of employed Muslim women, particularly in contexts marked by pronounced structural inequalities like in India, in order to inform broader efforts aimed at enhancing the ability of minority women to succeed within diverse and complex work-life settings.

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